

Quinazolin-4(3H)-ones of 2-[(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetic acid with substituted aryl acetamide and their microbial studies

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Abstract : Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of quinazolinones III₁₋₄₈ have been reported from 2-[(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetic acid and various substituted aryl acetamides at position two and three of quinazolinone nucleus respectively via benzoxazine intermediate I. All the compounds have been established on the basis of spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR) and elemental analysis.

Keywords : Benzoxazine, microbial studies, quinazolinones.

In the course of our work we have synthesized new quinazolinone systems consisting 2-[(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetic acid at position two and different substituted amines at third position, which can be exploited as bioactive compounds¹.

The reaction of 2-[2'-(2'',6''-dichlorophenylamino)]phenylmethyl-6-H/Br-3,1-benzoxazine-4(H)ones I with hydrazine hydrate and *p*-phenylene diamine in refluxing pyridine led to the formation of 2-[2'-(2'',6''-dichlorophenylamino)]phenylmethyl-4(3H)-oxo-3-aminoquinazoline II_a and 2-[2'-(2'',6''-dichlorophenylamino)]phenylmethyl-4(3H)-oxo-3-anilino-6-H/Br-quinazoline II_b. Synthesized compounds supported by elemental analysis and spectral data. The amide derivatives of quinazolinone exhibited a strong absorption band near 1660–1630 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of carbonyl group of secondary amide I, 1570–1515 cm⁻¹ amide II and 1300–1240 cm⁻¹ of amide III. The bands observed between 1700–1660 cm⁻¹ and 1720–1740 cm⁻¹ are due to cyclic ketone and acyclic ketone respectively. The ether linkage observed at 1144 cm⁻¹ indicates the confirmation of compound I. This peak of 1144 cm⁻¹ is replaced by the C–N linkage in compound II_a and II_b by 1295 cm⁻¹ and 1298 cm⁻¹. Other compounds have been characterized by spectral and elemental analyses.

Results and discussion

All the compounds reported in Table 1 were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity *in vitro* against *Pseudomonas sp.*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *Ceretium* and *C.*

Table 1. Physical properties of compound III₁₋₄₈

Compd. III	X	R	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1	H	H	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	194	31
2	H	2-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂	121	38
3	H	3-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂	132	44
4	H	4-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂	139 ^d	39
5	H	2-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	202	48
6	H	3-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	186	49
7	H	4-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	189	40
8	H	2-OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂	166	33
9	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂	154	55
10	H	2-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃	220 ^d	58
11	H	3-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃	194	59
12	H	4-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃	200 ^d	55
13	Br	H	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	193	39
14	Br	2-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Br	148	40
15	Br	3-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Br	159 ^d	43
16	Br	4-NO ₂	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Br	177	45
17	Br	2-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	209	64
18	Br	3-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	211	61
19	Br	4-CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	181	60
20	Br	2-OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	172	55
21	Br	4-OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	188	56
22	Br	2-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃ Br	175	44
23	Br	3-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃ Br	179	49
24	Br	4-Cl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃ Br	188	53
25	H	H	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	147	40

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

26	H	2-NO ₂	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂	130	46
27	H	3-NO ₂	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂	157	44
28	H	4-NO ₂	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂	177	44
29	H	2-CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	181	56
30	H	3-CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	200 ^d	51
31	H	4-CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂	195	39
32	H	2-OCH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂	197	62
33	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂	151	63
34	H	2-Cl	C ₃₆ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃	188	46
35	H	3-Cl	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃	191	45
36	H	4-Cl	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃	159	45
37	Br	H	C ₃₅ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	235 ^d	42
38	Br	2-NO ₂	C ₃₅ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Br	203 ^d	47
39	Br	3-NO ₂	C ₃₅ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Br	199	49
40	Br	4-NO ₂	C ₃₅ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂ Br	172	41
41	Br	2-CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	178	33
42	Br	3-CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	183	39
43	Br	4-CH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	149	38
44	Br	2-OCH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	217	63
45	Br	4-OCH ₃	C ₃₆ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₅ Cl ₂ Br	210	66
46	Br	2-Cl	C ₃₅ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃ Br	222	36
47	Br	3-Cl	C ₃₅ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃ Br	209	39
48	Br	4-Cl	C ₃₅ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₅ Cl ₃ Br	208	40

albicans respectively using cup plate method at 100 and 200 µg/ml concentrations. The activity was compared with known standards Penicillin-G, Ampicillin, Amoxicillin and Amphotericin-B.

From the screening results, **III_{11&12}** (R = 3-Cl, 4-Cl) showed good activity against gram positive bacteria *Pseudomonas sp.* and *B. subtilis* compared with standard drug penicillin-G at both the concentrations 100 and 200 µg/ml. **III₁₁** (R = 3-Cl) is also good active against gram negative bacteria *Ceretium* at 100 µg/ml concentration compared with penicillin-G. Compound **III_{19,22,24}** (R = 4-CH₃, 2-Cl, 4-Cl) shows significant activity against gram positive *Pseudomonas sp.* at 100 µg/ml concentration. While at 200 µg/ml concentration **III₂₃** (R = 3-Cl) shows significant activity against *B. subtilis* as compared with penicillin-G. Good activity was observed in **III₃₂** (R = 2-OCH₃) against gram positive *Pseudomonas sp.* compared with penicillin-G at 100 µg/ml concentration. Against gram negative bacterial species *E. coli*, only compound **III₃₄** (R = 2-Cl) is moderately active at 100 µg/ml concentration. Compound **III_{42,44,45}** (R = 3-CH₃, 2-OCH₃, 4-OCH₃) showed good activity against gram positive *Pseudomonas sp.* and *B. subtilis* bacterial species at 100 µg/ml concentration. Where as, at 200 µg/ml concentration, **III₄₄** (R = 2-OCH₃) activity increased spec-

Table 2. Spectral data of **III₁₋₄₈**

1	3351 (NH), 2950, 2830 (C-H), 1732 (C=O, acyclic), 1666 (C=O, cyclic), 1636, 1566, 1234 (amide I, II, III), 1309 (C-N), 798 (C-Cl)	9.30 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.20 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.92-6.53 (16H, m, Ar-H), 5.50 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.60 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.64 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
3	3339 (NH), 2925, 2840 (C-H), 1739 (C=O, acyclic), 1679 (C=O, cyclic), 1646, 1544, 1236 (amide I, II, III), 1581, 1365 (NO ₂ asym, sym), 1325 (C-N), 792 (C-Cl)	9.14 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.52 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.68-6.30 (15H, m, Ar-H), 5.18 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.51 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO), 3.20 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
9	3399 (NH), 2930, 2847 (C-H), 1735 (C=O, acyclic), 1674 (C=O, cyclic), 1648, 1566, 1240 (amide I, II, III), 1339 (C-N), 1206, 1106 (C-O-C), 780 (C-Cl)	9.45 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.41 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.25-6.10 (15H, m, Ar-H), 5.40 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.35 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.19 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
13	3337 (NH), 2958, 2815 (C-H), 1733 (C=O, acyclic), 1674 (C=O, cyclic), 1648, 1554, 1228 (amide I, II, III), 1320 (C-N), 798 (C-Cl), 617 (C-Br)	9.30 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.15 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.20-6.53 (15H, m, Ar-H), 5.10 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.51 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.10 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
17	3337 (NH), 2955, 2840 (C-H), 1733 (C=O, acyclic), 1674 (C=O, cyclic), 1648, 1554, 1228 (amide I, II, III), 1578, 1361 (NO ₂ asym, sym), 1320 (C-N), 792 (C-Cl)	9.45 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.66 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.52-6.51 (14H, m, Ar-H), 5.56 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.25 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.53 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂), 2.34 (3H, s, -CH ₃)
24	3342 (NH), 2948, 2817 (C-H), 1732 (C=O, acyclic), 1681 (C=O, cyclic), 1654, 1548, 1257 (amide I, II, III), 1327 (C-N), 790 (C-Cl), 617 (C-Br)	9.00 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.42 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.82-6.70 (14H, m, Ar-H), 5.11 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.44 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.55 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
25	3349 (NH), 2930, 2809 (C-H), 1729 (C=O, acyclic), 1677 (C=O, cyclic), 1621, 1544, 1221 (amide I, II, III), 1311 (C-N), 772 (C-Cl)	9.28 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.23 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.30-6.45 (19H, m, Ar-H), 5.55 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.62 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.63 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)

32	3342 (NH), 2956, 2800 (C-H), 1733 (C=O, acyclic), 1675 (C=O, cyclic), 1650, 1524, 1232 (amide I, II, III), 1318 (C-N), 1200, 1099 (C-O-C), 789 (C-Cl)	9.47 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.00 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.32-6.27 (18H, m, Ar-H), 5.24 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.52 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.29 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
34	3349 (NH), 2944, 2863 (C-H), 1726 (C=O, acyclic), 1678 (C=O, cyclic), 1642, 1530, 1228 (amide I, II, III), 1318 (C-N), 790 (C-Cl)	9.18 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.16 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.70-6.49 (18H, m, Ar-H), 5.63 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.54 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.00 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
39	3369 (NH), 2932, 2823 (C-H), 1728 (C=O, acyclic), 1676 (C=O, cyclic), 1649, 1543, 1240 (amide I, II, III), 1501, 1302 (NO ₂ asym. sym), 1313 (C-N)	9.45 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.40 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.36-6.70 (18H, m, Ar-H), 5.10 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.32 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.23 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)
42	3381 (NH), 2933, 2810 (C-H), 1733 (C=O, acyclic), 1670 (C=O, cyclic), 1633, 1539, 1230 (amide I, II, III), 1314 (C-N), 792 (C-Cl), 618 (C-Br)	9.20 (1H, s, -NH-), 8.20 (1H, s, -CONH-), 7.53-6.24 (18H, m, Ar-H), 5.21 (1H, s, -CH ₂ -NH-N-), 4.88 (2H, s, -CH ₂ CO-), 3.54 (2H, s, Ar-CH ₂)

Note

tacularly in comparison with standard drug penicillin-G. Against gram negative bacteria *E. coli*, **III**₄₈ (R = 4-Cl) showed good activity at 100 and 200 µg/ml concentrations compared with penicillin-G. Compound **III**₄₆ (R = 2-Cl), the activity increased with increase the concentration. Against *C. albicans*, **III**₄₆ (R = 2-Cl) showed good activity at 200 µg/ml concentration as compared with standard drug amphotericin-B.

Compounds containing chloro and bromo substituents showed significant activity and moderate to good activity for methoxy and bromo substituents. It is concluded that bromo derivatives are more active than unsubstituted compounds.

Experimental

M.p.s were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds were checked by TLC. IR absorption spectra was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 838 FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr pellet and ¹H NMR spectra was recorded in chloroform on Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) instrument (chemical shift in δ ppm). The required compound 2-[(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetic acid was prepared by reacting *o*-chlorophenylacetic acid with excess of 2,6-dichloroaniline in DMF-xylene in the presence of K₂CO₃, KI and Cu₂Cl₂ at 150–152 °C for 5 h².

The compound 2-[(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetyl chloride was prepared by known method³. 2-[2'-(2'',6''-Dichlorophenylamino)]phenylmethyl-6-H/bromo-3,1-benzoxazine-4(H)ones **I** was also prepared by reported method⁴.

2-[2'-(2'',6''-Dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-4-(3H)-oxo-3-aminoquinazoline **II**_a :

To a mixture of 2-[2'-(2'',6''-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-3,1-benzoxazine-4(H)-one **I** (0.001 mol) and hydrazinehydrate (0.001 mol) in 20 ml of pyridine was heated at 180–200 °C in an oil bath for 5–6 h. After completion of the reaction, the oily mass was slowly poured onto crushed acidic (HCl, 10 ml) ice-cold water with occasional stirring. The obtained product was filtered and washed several times with water. The crude product was dried and crystallized from ethanol.

2-[2'-(2'',6''-Dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-4-(3H)-oxo-3-quinazolinylamino-N-(2-chlorophenyl)aceta-

mid **III**₁₀ :

A mixture of **II**_a (0.01 mol), *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-chloroacetamide (0.01 mol) and methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The excess solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the solution poured over crushed ice. The solid was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallized from absolute ethanol. Similarly other compounds could be prepared.

2-[2'-(2'',6''-Dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-4-(3H)-oxo-3-anilino-6-bromoquinazolin **II**_b :

To a mixture of 2-[2'-(2'',6''-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-6-bromo-3,1-benzoxazine-4(H)-one **I** (0.001 mol) and *p*-phenylenediamine (0.001 mol) in 20 ml of pyridine is heated at 180–200 °C in an oil bath for 5–6 h. After completion of the reaction, the oily mass was slowly poured onto crushed acidic (HCl, 10 ml) ice-cold water with occasional stirring. The obtained product was filtered and washed several times with water. The crude product was dried and crystallized from acetone.

2-[2'-(2'',6''-Dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-4-(3H)-oxo-3-(6-bromoquinazolinylanilino)-N-(3-methylphenyl)acetamide **III**₄₂ :

A mixture of **II**_b (0.01 mol), *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-chloroacetamide (0.01 mol) and methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The excess solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the solution poured over crushed ice. The solid was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and recrystallized from absolute ethanol. Similarly other compounds could be prepared.

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